

andacc User Guide (version 1.0)

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Abstract

This guide provides instructions on how to use the **andacc** package, intended for applying Anderson Acceleration, a sequence acceleration method originally created in the 1960s, to Earth System Model (ESM) spin-up problems. By treating the spin up problem as a fixed point problem, and considering the underlying ESM to be our black box fixed point function, we are able to utilize Anderson's algorithm to increase convergence speed. This method has now been successfully applied to MITgcm-BLING, NEMO-PISCES, NEMO-MEDUSA, JULES, and CLM.

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1 Introduction

andacc is a Python package designed to solve fixed point problems through Anderson Acceleration[1], a sequence acceleration method originally designed by D.G. Anderson in the 1960s to solve integral equations. The focus of this user guide will be on using the **andacc** package for earth system model (ESM) spin up, although the Anderson code presented here is general and could work on simpler cases. The primary benefit of Anderson Acceleration over other spin up acceleration methods is that it is essentially a “black box” method, in that, in general, the underlying earth system model code need not be modified before use. This method has demonstrated significant acceleration across both General Circulation Models (GCM) and land models, namely MITgcm-BLING, NEMO-PISCES, NEMO-MEDUSA, JULES, and CLM. The underlying Anderson Acceleration code is based on the implementation of Walker and Ni in [10], and readers are referred there for the basics of Anderson Acceleration. Here, we focus on its application to ESMs.

1.1 Mathematical Background

In the most broad mathematical sense we are seeking the solution to a fixed point problem,

$$\mathbf{x}(T) = \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(0)). \quad (1)$$

For our case solving 1 refers to finding a seasonally repeating equilibrium solution of the user’s ESM of choice, where \mathbf{x} is a column vector representation of the tracer field at all grid points as in [4] and [5], and $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})$ represents running the model itself for one year, where we assume the ESM has a period of $T = 1$ year.

The classical approach to solving a fixed point problem such as 1 is the *Fixed Point* or *Picard* iteration, given by

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}_k). \quad (2)$$

The upside of the Picard iteration is its simplicity, although that is countered by the downside slow convergence to a fixed point. Various methods have been proposed to accelerate the convergence of 2, and we refer an interested reader to the extensive mathematics literature such as [2] or [9] for thorough coverage of a myriad of methods. Here, however, we focus on so called *Anderson Acceleration*, an extrapolation method developed in the 1960s by D.G. Anderson in which the next iterate is chosen to be a linear combination of the m previous iterates so that the residual, $\mathbf{g}(x) - \mathbf{x}$, of a linear function \mathbf{g} is minimized.

Mathematically we may state Anderson Acceleration, hence forth referred to as *AA*, as

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = (1 - \beta_k) \sum_{i=0}^{m_k} \alpha_i^{(k)} \mathbf{x}_{k-m_k+i} + \beta_k \sum_{i=0}^{m_k} \alpha_i^{(k)} \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}_{k-m_k+i}), \quad (3)$$

where β_k is the *damping parameter*, which can be thought of as a control on step size, m_k is the *memory parameter*, which is the number of previous iterates we are using in the linear combination for the next iterate, and the weights $\alpha_i^{(k)}$ ’s are found by minimizing the norm of the weighted residual at the k^{th} step, i.e. solving

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize} \quad \left\| \sum_{j=0}^{m_k} \alpha_j^k \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_{k-m_k+j}) \right\|_2^2, \\ & \text{subject to} \quad \sum_{j=0}^{m_k} \alpha_j^k = 1, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) := \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{x}$. In practice 4 is recast as an unconstrained least squares problem, interested readers are directed to [11, 10] for details of the reformulation. It is possible to vary β and m adaptively, but for our work we take them to be constant across all iterative steps. Before continuing we note that it is clear that AA reduces to the standard Fixed Point iteration by setting $m = 0$ and $\beta = 1$.

Figure 1: Basic schematic of the **andacc** workflow. The algorithm sits as a wrapper outside of the ESM, on each iteration it reads model output, applies sequence acceleration techniques, then uses the accelerated iterate as the initial condition for the next model call.

1.2 General Structure

The **andacc** package is designed to sit as a wrapper outside of the user’s ESM of choice. The general structure of the method is a Python wrapper that runs the underlying ESM for one year at a time using the model executable, reads the model state from the ESM restart files, transforms this data into a format that is necessary to apply Anderson Acceleration, uses the mathematics in Section 1.1 to find a state that is closer to equilibrium, and then manually adjusts the ESM restart files to insert that state before starting this cycle again. The general structure is illustrated by the schematic in Figure 1, with a more detailed workflow schematic shown in Figure 2. This workflow relies on a few main structures, functions, and scripts which are described briefly below, and in more detail later in the documentation.

1.2.1 Data File

Arguably the most important file for **andacc** is the ‘data’ file, an hdf5 file created with the python script **make_data_for_*.py**. Within the algorithm a large amount of information is passed between functions in a dictionary structure called **data**, **dataAA**, or similar. This dictionary structure contains information like the names of the tracers being accelerated, their dimensions, the map between model tracer data fields (typically a 3D array, but also 2D and 1D), and the Anderson iterate **x**, the land mask for global ocean models, the mpi call necessary to actually run the model, etc.

The **make_data_for_*.py** file deals with the initial set up of this data structure, and creates the file storing most of the information that gets used in the algorithm (some is assigned in the main driver). The **make_data_for_*.py** file is also where a user sets which tracers to accelerate. The user defines a list of BGC tracer names corresponding to those used in the model’s restart files. From there, the python script pulls the necessary information from user specified files, e.g. the **mesh_mask** file to get the land mask for NEMO-MEDUSA, **hFacC** file for MITgcm-Bling, and model restart files to get tracer dimesnions.

1.2.2 Utility Functions

Interaction with model restart files is handled by utility functions defined in ***_andacc_utils.py**. These functions are for reading and writing to model restart files and for transformation between different **andacc** specific linear algebra structures. In general, when applying **andacc** to a new model these functions must be rewritten to account for differences in restart file format. The work is typically minimal and these functions are already available for NEMO-MEDUSA, JULES, CLM, and MITgcm.

1.2.3 Timestepper

The Python file `timestepperfunc_*.py` contains the “timestepper” function which is used to actually run the underlying ESM. The timestepper function serves as the actual wrapper around the underlying ESM, and typically applies optional preprocessing steps, runs the underlying ESM, and applies optional post processing steps, although a user can adjust this function to communicate with the model however is desired. Within the main driver `run_AndAcc*.py` the fixed point function `g` is set to be the timestepper function. In general, when applying AA to a new model the timestepper function must be rewritten slightly to ensure compatibility, but the main structure remains in place.

1.2.4 Main Driver

The main `andacc` driver is the file `run_AndAcc*.py`. This is where algorithm parameters are set, `andacc.py` is called, and the vast majority of user edits will take place. Typically this is structured as follows: basic settings, parameter settings, reading restarts/instantiating structures, defining diagnostic functions, calling `andacc.py`, and post processing steps. The format of this driver has small variations between ocean models, but from experience thus far remains relatively unchanged from ocean model to ocean model. For land, however, there are significant differences in the way the driver operates from model to model. It has been found that there are more fundamental differences in the way JULES and CLM operate compared to say MITgcm Bling and NEMO-MEDUSA. Example drivers are available for all models, and the user may compare workflow.

It is also worth emphasizing that there is a fundamental difference in the main driver structure when comparing ocean models to land models. Because, in general, soil columns are independent during spin up of land models one instance of `andacc` is run for *each* independent soil column. For an ocean model one instance of `andacc` is run for the entire ocean, and all points evolve dependent on each other. The user may refer to Section 4.5 for more information on the structure of the main driver for their model of choice.

1.3 Features

This section highlights some of the useful features built into the `andacc` code.

1.3.1 Restarting

One of the most important features for `andacc` is the ability to stop and restart a spin up. Because of the nature of long spin ups and HPC rules, it is almost always necessary to break up the spin up into smaller portions. With `andacc` this is very simple; the main driver will keep track of elapsed wall time, so the user can set a desired limit to match with what is requested in the HPC submission script. If the specified wall time limit is reached, the algorithm will stop and the main AA driver will write out restart files containing the current state of the algorithm. The user then only needs to resubmit the job script and the driver will read the restart files and pick up where it left off.

1.3.2 Selective Acceleration

Regardless of the underlying Earth system model `andacc` will restructure tracer data into a column vector. E.g. for an ocean model where all tracers are defined on a 3 dimensional ocean grid, the package will map all of the specified tracers into one long column vector \mathbf{x} , the format the data needs to be in for the linear algebra operations taking place inside the code to determine the next iterate. This also opens the door to the possibility of selective acceleration through what is called the \mathbf{y} vector. In general `andacc` is always rerunning the same year; i.e. if we are running year 1850 to 1851 `andacc` will read from the 1851 restart file and write to the 1850 restart file on each iteration. The default is that any desired tracers

will be accelerated, and the accelerated iterate written back to the initial condition file (the 1850 restart in this example). However, a user may want to passively copy certain tracers, or passively accelerate certain tracers. The **y** vector allows this. The user may specify which tracers, or even geographic filters, that they want to be simply copied over each iteration in the `make_data_for_*.py` script. The user may also select that the tracers in **y** are passively accelerated, meaning that the Anderson direction is chosen from exclusively the **x** vector, but applied to both **x** and **y**.

Remark 1 This feature has not been used often so far. While it provides the option for hyper specific acceleration it has not been shown to have a significant impact on performance in most cases.

1.3.3 Convergence Checking

The standard AA convergence criteria based on residual value is difficult to assign a priori. Further, the full `andacc` residual is based on the norm of the model state of sometimes more than 30 tracers so often not physically meaningful. There is generally some kind of external diagnostic that provides a better indicator of whether the model is ‘spun up.’ For example, CMIP indicates air-sea CO₂ flux should be < 0.01PgC/yr for an ocean model to be deemed spun up. Therefore a better way to track convergence is to keep track of the CO₂ flux on the fly, and flag to the algorithm once this has reached below the threshold. This is possible with `andacc` by specifying an external convergence check function in the main driver `run_AndAcc*.py`. This function is then called as a post-processing step in the `timestepperfunc_*.py` function, and if external convergence criteria has been met `andacc` stops.

1.3.4 Utility Functions

Various utility functions are included in the code to make operations more simple. In `andacc.py` the functions `load` and `save` are defined, which are used to read and write hdf5 files. These are extremely helpful for writing the data file or restarts, which contain information that typically is difficult to format as hdf5. These functions make reading and writing extremely easy, and should be used to read or write any `andacc` specific files.

Also included in the package is the file `*_andacc_utils.py` which contains all of the model specific I/O functions as well as utility functions to move between data structures inside the code. These functions are typically named to coincide with the model, and the read/write functions must be rewritten for application to a new model. For example, for CLM the function to write to model restarts is called `writeToCLMRestart`, and for NEMO-MEDUSA the function is called `writeToNEMORestart`.

1.3.5 Tracer Scaling

Another feature of `andacc` is the ability to apply a scaling to certain BGC tracers. Not all BGC tracers have similar scales for the values they take on, so when all tracers are condensed into one long column vector it could be beneficial, from a mathematical standpoint, to scale a tracer’s value up or down. Tracer scaling is handled in the `make_data_for_*.py` file, and does not alter the actual value of the tracer.

Remark 2 Algorithm performance has been found to be *very* sensitive to tracer scaling, and further, it has not been intuitive. The most sensible mathematical approach is to scale everything to $\mathcal{O}(1)$, but in testing this has not worked. Generally algorithm performance is quite good without any scaling, so it is suggested that the user begin with no scaling.

1.4 Notation

To simplify notation moving forward “AA” will refer to Anderson Acceleration, “DI” will refer to a direct time integration of the model,¹ “data file” refers to the specific attribute file created by `make_data_for_*.py`, and “years” will correspond to iteration count as the underlying earth system model is run for 1 year each AA iteration.

Figure 2: More detailed schematic of the AA workflow showing the path to interaction with the underlying ESM from the main driver. `sAA` is a dictionary structure containing the ‘state’ of the model in `andacc` formats, i.e. `x`, defined in Section 3.2.

2 Quickstart Guide

This section provides a rapid fire overview of the procedure for using `andacc` on an ESM. Set up procedures are described in the context of NEMO-MEDUSA, although the general steps will be similar for other ESMs. Further details on all of the steps and files discussed here are available throughout the remainder of this documentation.

2.1 ESM Set Up

Before applying `andacc` the user’s ESM needs to be setup to run for one year at a time using yearly periodic forcing. In the context of NEMO-MEDUSA this means the user needs a spun up physical ocean state, and needs to set the namelists to read the same physics restart files every iteration. For land models the user must ensure the same atmospheric forcing year is used at each iteration. These steps ensure that a seasonally equilibrium condition is well defined, and is crucial for `andacc` to work. It is suggested the user also perturb slightly away from any default model conditions by running the underlying ESM for approximately 10 years for ocean models or 50 to 100 years for land models. For NEMO-MEDUSA a user also needs to separately run the model for a few timesteps (not years, model time steps) on a

¹Also known as a Picard Iteration, called Native Dynamics for CLM

single core to generate a combined mesh mask file. The combined mesh mask file is needed by the `make_data_for_*.py` script to mask out land points from tracer fields.

2.2 Python Files and Functions

The Python files included with the `andacc` package need to be copied to the user's ESM `run/` directory. Moving forward all interaction with the underlying ESM is handled through the `andacc` workflow.

2.2.1 `make_data_for_*.py`

The user creates the `data` file, an hdf5 file containing a dictionary including model specific information such as tracer names, dimensions, and the underlying mpi command to run the model, by running `python make_data_for_nemo_medusa.py`. The user will need to adjust this Python script to ensure the correct tracer names are set for their model and the correct grid mask file is read from in order to mask out land points. Available are versions for NEMO-MEDUSA, NEMO-PISCES, MITgcm-Bling, CLM-CENTURY, CLM-MIMICS, and JULES

2.2.2 `timestepperfunc_*.py`

The `timestepperfunc_*.py` function is the wrapper that sits around the underlying ESM and is called at each iteration of `andacc` as the fixed point function. It's purpose, as named, is to run the model for one year, the equivalent of applying the fixed point function. The user may adjust this function to interact with the underlying ESM however is desired, but for NEMO-MEDUSA no modification is necessary from the included file. Also included are versions for MITgcm, CLM, and JULES.

2.2.3 `andacc`

`andacc.py` is where the underlying Anderson Acceleration algorithm and loop is housed. The `andacc` function is called from the `run_AndAcc*.py` driver, and returns either a final solution or flag to write restarts depending on if HPC wall time limits are reached before convergence. The underlying algorithm closely follows the implementation of Walker and Ni in [10]. The user does not need to adjust or edit this file.

2.2.4 `run_AndAcc*.py`

`run_AndAcc*.py` is the main driver file. It's purpose is to set algorithm parameters, define checkpointing and external convergence check functions if desired, and call `andacc`. In the main driver is additionally where the user will set `data.run_model_cmd`, which should be the mpi command to run the underlying ESM executable. If `andacc` returns because of reaching a wall time limit, `run_AndAcc*.py` will write restart files so the user can resubmit an HPC jobscript and continue the spin up in a totally deterministic way.

2.3 Running a spin up with `andacc`

Running `andacc` is very simple, the user need only create an HPC scheduler submission script that loads appropriate modules, and calls `python run_AndAcc_for_*.py`. Typically an HPC venv or module containing SciPy and other basic Python numerical packages automatically contains all of the necessary requirements, but for land models a user must also pip install `cvxopt` [8]. It is common practice to send the run output into a log file by adding `>> log_aa` after the Python call in the runscript, as `andacc` periodically writes out diagnostics so the user can check on algorithm progress. If wall time limits are reached and `run_AndAcc*.py` writes restart files the user need only resubmit the jobscript.

3 Dictionary Structures and Definitions

This section explains some of the important structures that are used throughout **andacc**. The main purpose of these structures is a way to pass information about algorithm parameters, model structure, and model state more succinctly. We begin with the two most important structures, the “data” file dictionary, and the Anderson Acceleration object dictionary.

3.1 dataAA

Within **andacc.py** a dictionary class called `DotDict()` is defined to make storing and accessing dictionary information easier throughout the package. This dictionary is identical to the standard Python dictionary but with the added ability to access keys with a ‘dot’ notation, i.e. `data.numTracers` is equivalent to `data['numTracers']` and can be accessed however the user prefers. The `data` or `dataAA` dictionary is created with `make_data_for_*.py` and stores primarily model specific information that is necessary for **andacc** to run properly. As mentioned in Section 1.2.1 this includes tracer names and dimensions, land masks for ocean models, tracer scalings, restart file names, the mpi command to run the model, pre or post processing commands, and the maps between a 3 dimensional model grid and the column vector \mathbf{x} .

Figure 3: Masking and flattening a 3d global array into a column vector, indices may be ordered differently depending on which flattening method is used, in our case this is not important as long as it is kept track of. For the ocean we want to filter out the indices of all the land points, which we do by applying a boolean mask before flattening. Blue indicates a point associated with the ocean, and red a land point.

The data file also contains information on the map between \mathbf{x} and v , a 2 dimensional array containing flattened tracer data in each column. It is easiest to understand these maps with an example, so let’s consider a generic ocean model. In order to go from the model restart file data to the AA vector \mathbf{x} the first step in is to apply a boolean mask to separate out all points in the 3d discretized approximation of the earth that are associated with the ocean. From there, using NumPy’s built in function `flatnonzero` we obtain the indices of the ocean components of the vector obtained by flattening the 3d array. A schematic diagram of the masking and flattening process for one tracer field is given in Figure 3.1. The flattening process happens for all ocean tracer fields, which are then stored as columns in the matrix v , shown in equation 5. v has dimensions $\text{nb} \times \text{numTracers}$, where nb is the total number of “wet” points.

$$v = \begin{bmatrix} | & | & | & \dots \\ \text{OXY} & \text{DIC} & \text{ALK} & \dots \\ | & | & | & \dots \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

As indicated in Section 1.3.2 **andacc** allows for AA on particular aspects of the tracer spin up problem. It is possible to separate out, using utility functions, specific parts of v , which are then used in **andacc** to determine the best AA step. This is again best illustrated with an ocean model example; suppose we have four tracers, Oxygen (OXY), Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC), Total Alkalinity (ALK), and Iron nutrient (FER). Our matrix v would then be

$$v = \begin{bmatrix} (\text{OXY})_1 & (\text{DIC})_1 & (\text{ALK})_1 & (\text{FER})_1 \\ (\text{OXY})_2 & (\text{DIC})_2 & (\text{ALK})_2 & (\text{FER})_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ (\text{OXY})_{nb} & (\text{DIC})_{nb} & (\text{ALK})_{nb} & (\text{FER})_{nb} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where as before nb is the total number of wet points. Now suppose that in this situation FER evolves far faster than say DIC, and shallow ocean OXY evolves far faster than deep ocean OXY. This package gives the ability to separate these components out so that Anderson Acceleration can select steps based on only the slowest evolving manifolds. In Equation 6 let indices 1 through k indicate shallow ocean components, and $k + 1$ through nb indicate deep ocean points. We flatten and split v into fast and slow evolving components, i.e.

$$v = \begin{bmatrix} (\text{OXY})_1 & (\text{DIC})_1 & (\text{ALK})_1 & (\text{FER})_1 \\ (\text{OXY})_2 & (\text{DIC})_2 & (\text{ALK})_2 & (\text{FER})_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ (\text{OXY})_k & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ (\text{OXY})_{k+1} & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ (\text{OXY})_{nb} & (\text{DIC})_{nb} & (\text{ALK})_{nb} & (\text{FER})_{nb} \end{bmatrix} \xrightarrow{v2xy} x = \begin{bmatrix} (\text{OXY})_{k+1} \\ (\text{OXY})_{k+2} \\ \vdots \\ (\text{OXY})_{nb} \\ (\text{DIC})_1 \\ \vdots \\ (\text{DIC})_{nb} \\ (\text{ALK})_1 \\ \vdots \\ (\text{ALK})_{nb} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

$$\text{and } y = \begin{bmatrix} (\text{OXY})_1 \\ (\text{OXY})_2 \\ \vdots \\ (\text{OXY})_k \\ (\text{FER})_1 \\ (\text{FER})_2 \\ \vdots \\ (\text{FER})_{nb} \end{bmatrix},$$

where red indicates a slow evolving component and blue a quickly evolving component, and $v2xy$ is the utility function to transform from v to \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} . Now \mathbf{x} contains all slow evolving components, and \mathbf{y} all fast evolving components, and in the acceleration algorithm we make all acceleration decisions *solely* based on accelerating \mathbf{x} to a fixed point, and the user can specify if the acceleration direction and step is applied to \mathbf{y} or if \mathbf{y} is evolved with a direct integration. Note that for the ocean all steps need be applied to \mathbf{y} to ensure tracer conservation. There are complimentary utility functions to restructure the vectors \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} back into a set of 3d arrays. Further, as indicated in Section 1.3.5, the user can apply a scaling to \mathbf{x} during the transformation $v2xy$. This can be beneficial if certain tracers have values with significantly different orders of magnitude.

3.1.1 External Convergence Function

The user has the option to define a function for checking convergence of **andacc** by means of an external diagnostic. This function, typically called `externalConvergenceCheck` and

assigned to the `data` structure, is defined by the user in the main `run_AndAcc*.py` driver. This function is designed to allow the user to monitor model diagnostics and indicate convergence even if the AA residual has not met the specified tolerance. From experience this is a much better way to determine convergence than AA residual, and is in line with how ESM's are typically analyzed for convergence, e.g. air-sea CO₂ flux reaching below 0.1 PgC/yr for CMIP ocean models. For land models changes in total carbon stock are often used to determine when a model is spun up, but because of the inherently larger jumps that `andacc` takes an instantaneous difference is not a good measure. Instead an average change is calculated by taking the slope of a line through a user specified number of points, and when that slope is acceptably close to zero, convergence is declared.

3.2 Anderson Acceleration Object

The `AndersonAccelerationObj` is another dictionary instantiated using the `DotDict` class so that a user can access keys with the standard Python format or with dot notation as described in Section 3.1. It is designed to hold algorithm and model state information as well as algorithm parameters. Typically in the driver this is instantiated as `s`, `sAA`, or similar to indicate the 'state' of the algorithm. This state dictionary is always passed into `andacc` as an input as a concise way to include `x`, `y`, the matrices defined by the least squares problem 4, residual history, the values from `AAparams`, and algorithm iterative history. Collecting all of this information into a single object makes it easier to stop and restart, as all that must be saved is `sAA`.

3.3 AAparams

In the main driver `run_AndAcc*.py` all of the AA specific parameters can be set using the dictionary `AAparams`. This dictionary is then added to the state `sAA` described in the previous section within the main `andacc` function call. The user could in theory manually add the algorithm parameters to `sAA`, but for readability and clarity it is preferred by the authors to define this additional dictionary in the main driver. Table 3.3 gives definitions for some of the primary parameters to be set in this structure, the user can also see the source code in `andacc.py` to see all of the possible options.

3.4 histParams

Finally, the `histParams` dictionary indicates to `andacc` when to write historical checkpoints, and what to include. In `run_AndAcc*.py` the user defines a checkpointing function and assigns it to `histParams`. This function can be called at the user's desired frequency to write out diagnostics, current solutions, etc. This feature is most beneficial for testing purposes, as it allows the user to track the progress of all tracers towards the final spun up state, but if using `andacc` for production spin up it will likely be less helpful.

3.4.1 CheckpointingFunction

The `checkpointingFunction` is defined in the main `run_AndAcc*.py` driver and assigned to `histParams`. Each iteration in `andacc` the checkpointing function is called, allowing the user to write out solutions at each iteration to view the path towards convergence to a spun up state. Additionally, this function can be used to write out desired diagnostics. Below is an annotated example of the checkpointing function for NEMO-MEDUSA.

```

1 #####
2 # FUNCTION DEFINITIONS #
3 #####
4 def checkpointingFunction(i,s):
5     fn="aa_co2flux_{:04d}".format(i)

```

Table 1: AA parameters to set in main driver.

<code>wallTime</code>	The limit for wall time used, should be set with a small buffer to the HPC requested wall time to ensure time for writing restart files at the end.
<code>mMax</code>	Anderson memory parameter. This controls how many previous iterates are used to determine the next step
<code>itmax</code>	The maximum number of iterations allowed
<code>beta</code>	Damping parameter, this controls whether a ‘full’ AA step is taken or partial
<code>rto1</code>	Residual tolerance for convergence
<code>atol</code>	Absolute tolerance for convergence
<code>restartAAPeriodic</code>	Will flush memory history and restart AA as set. Has been shown to be helpful in ocean models, not so for land
<code>applyAAtoY</code>	There is an option in the code to store some tracer values in a vector called <code>y</code> which gets passively accelerated. This determines whether to apply the acceleration or simply do direct integration. This is not being used in any form currently, and is therefore not listed on the main driver parameters but is a feature that could be used in the future. See Section 1.3.2 for more.

```

6 CO2FLUX=NIO.read2dNEMOField("CO2FLUX", "ORCA2_1y_00010101_00011231_diag2d.nc
   ", isGlobal=True)
7 # Integrate globally to get total flux in PgC/year } Read MEDUSA CO2 flux and
8 tcflx=np.sum(data.dA*CO2FLUX)*12/1e15 } globally integrate, write to h5 file
9 to_save = {'iter_':i, 'tcflx': tcflx} } to use in analysis
10 save(to_save,fn)
11
12 with np.printoptions(suppress=False):
13     print("CO2flux: ",tcflx)
14     if (i % 10 == 0): ← Every 10 iterations we save the model solution to an h5 file for analysis
15         fn="spinup_solution_{:04d}".format(i)
16         res_hist = s.res_hist[i, :]
17         to_save = {'iter_':i, 'x': s.x, 'y': s.y, 'res_hist': res_hist, 'tcflx':
18             tcflx}
19         save(to_save,fn)
20         fn = "ORCA2_00005840_restart_trc.nc_{:04d}".format(i)
21         os.system("cp -p ORCA2_00005840_restart_trc.nc " + fn)
22     if (i>0) and (i % 10 == 0): ← Every 10 iterations we also save a full spin up checkpoint.
23         fn="aa_restart_checkpoint" This includes far more information than the solution above.
24         iter0=s.iter0 Allows for a restart without loss of progress if model crashes.
25         s.iter0=i+1 This feature is mainly used in testing not production mode.
26         save(s,fn)
27         s.iter0 = iter0_
28         os.system("cp -p ORCA2_00005840_restart_trc.nc ORCA2_00005840_restart_trc.
29             nc_checkpoint")
30     return None ← Assign to the histParams dictionary in the main driver
histParams.checkpointingFunction=checkpointingFunction

```

Listing 1: Example checkpointing function from NEMO-MEDUSA.

4 Setup

4.1 Requirements

One of the biggest benefits of **andacc** compared alternative spin up acceleration methods is that, in general, it is not necessary to alter the underlying BGC source code; it is essentially a black box method. Further, acceleration is handled in a python driver, with very few dependencies. The user need only have Python 3.8+, with the packages NumPy, netCDF4, h5py, and SciPy and for land models cvxopt and lsqin. Often these are loadable on an HPC through modules or activation of a common venv. The user should also have the Python files from the **andacc** package present in the ESM “run” directory.

4.2 Earth System Model Settings

The underlying model needs to be set up to run for one year at a time with yearly repeating forcing conditions. Having a yearly repeating forcing is critical for the success of **andacc** as without a yearly periodic forcing there is no hope of a well defined fixed point for **andacc** to converge to. Additionally, the user needs to ensure that the model won’t raise errors for overly large jumps in tracer value. To illustrate this, consider CLM’s CN balance check. The allowed threshold in the underlying biogeochemical source code must be increased before spin up with **andacc** because the inherently bigger steps **andacc** takes towards a final equilibrium solution will instantly violate the default tolerance and crash the model.

For ocean models a spun up physical state of the model is necessary as well. To get this users should spin up their model of choice with biogeochemistry *turned off*. The user then will have a good estimate of ocean dynamics and **andacc** will accelerate the more computationally intensive BGC spin up while using the same spun up physical restart files every iteration. Currently in development is a way to apply Anderson Acceleration to spinning up the physical variables, and a user may reach out to the authors with further questions.

For both land and ocean models the user should run a short period of DI to move slightly away from the initial conditions of the model. It has been found that turning on **andacc** immediately can cause some issues, but typically a short adjustment period is sufficient to lose memory of the initial condition. Generally this adjustment can be as few as 10 years for ocean models, land models typically require ≈ 100 .

4.3 Data File

Section 3.1 gives a comprehensive definition and explanation on the data file, here we focus on what edits may be necessary to apply this package to a new ESM. When applying **andacc** to a new ocean model necessary edits will likely be very limited. For example, from MITgcm-Bling to NEMO-MEDUSA the general structure remains largely the same, just pulling from different mesh file names and accounting for restart file formats. It is slightly complicated when running a version of NEMO-MEDUSA with sediment tracers, as **andacc** then needs a 2d mask in addition to the standard mask in order to mask the sediment tracers, but this is handled with only a few lines of code. Listing 2 below gives an annotated overview of an example `make_data_for_*.py` file for NEMO-MEDUSA.

Land models tend to have more difference and require more extensive rewriting. The JULES `make_data_for_*.py` file follows a very similar structure to the ocean models, but for CLM the PFT, column, gridcell hierarchy provided an added complication. It is difficult to give a general rule of thumb for what modifications will be needed, but the user needs to ensure that `make_data_for_*.py` writes the following information to the `data` dictionary structure:

1. Tracer names to be accelerated as named in the model restart file
2. Total number of tracers

3. Tracer dimensions
4. Total number of tracer data values
5. The land mask for ocean models
6. Tracers in the \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} vectors
7. Any desired tracer scalings
8. The index maps from model grid to the matrix v and the column vector \mathbf{x}

It is suggested that the user begin from an example `make_data_for_*.py` file and make edits as necessary.

```

1 import numpy as np
2 import netCDF4 as nc
3 from andacc import (
4     DotDict,
5     save,
6     load
7 )
8 from nemo_andacc_utils import NEMOIO
9
10 NIO=NEMOIO() ← Instantiate the utility class to use for reading in model files
11 tmask=NIO.read3dNEMOField("tmask", "mesh_mask", isGlobal=False)
12
13 # In the following tmask generally refers to the land/sea mask
14 # and Idx (m2vIb) maps the wet points of the model to "v"
15
16 sedmask=tmask[:,0,:,:)
17
18 Idxt=np.flatnonzero(tmask) ← Keep the indices to map between flattened and global arrays
19 Idxs=np.flatnonzero(sedmask) ←
20
21 tr = ['CHN', 'CHD', 'PHN', 'PHD', 'ZMI', 'ZME', 'DIN', 'SIL', 'FER', 'DET', 'PDS', 'DTC',
22       'DiC', 'ALK', 'OXY'] ← Define the names of the tracers to be accelerated
23 wtr = ['None']*len(tr)*2
24 wtr[0:len(wtr):2] = ['TRB'+tr[i] for i in range(len(tr))]
25 wtr[1:len(wtr):2] = ['TRN'+tr[i] for i in range(len(tr))]
26
27 tr = ['SED_N', 'SED_FE', 'SED_SI', 'SED_C', 'SED_CA']
28 sedtr = ['None']*len(tr)*2
29 sedtr[0:len(sedtr):2] = ['B_'+tr[i] for i in range(len(tr))]
30 sedtr[1:len(sedtr):2] = ['N_'+tr[i] for i in range(len(tr))] } Specific to MEDUSA
31                               } with sediment tracers
32
33 Idx=[Idxt, Idxs]
34
35 data=DotDict() ← Create dictionary structure to assign below
36 data.tmask=[tmask, sedmask] ← Assign to DotDict with dot notation.
37 data.tmaskId=[0 for itr in range(len(wtr))] + [1 for itr in range(len(sedtr))]
38 data.trNames=wtr+sedtr
39 data.numTracers=len(data.trNames)
40 data.trnb=[len(Idx[data.tmaskId[itr]]) for itr in range(data.numTracers)]
41 data.trnb=np.array(data.trnb)
42 data.nb=max(data.trnb)
43 data.m2vIb=Idx
44
45 vscaleFac=np.ones(data.numTracers) ← Here we apply no tracer scaling
46 data.XTovScaleFac=np.diag(vscaleFac)
47 data.vToXScaleFac=np.diag(1./vscaleFac)
48
49 # Add surface area to data file for getting global co2 flux
50 e1t=NIO.read2dNEMOField("e1t", "mesh_mask", isGlobal=False)
51 e2t=NIO.read2dNEMOField("e2t", "mesh_mask", isGlobal=False)
52 dA=e1t*e2t
53 data.dA=dA

```

```

52
53 vib=np.zeros(shape=(data.nb,data.numTracers))
54 for itr in range(data.numTracers):
55     nbt=data.trnb[itr]
56     vib[0:nbt,itr]=1
57
58 data.x2vIb=np.flatnonzero(vib==1)
59 data.y2vIb=np.flatnonzero(vib==2)
60
61
62 save(data, "data_for_nemo_medusa_with_sed")

```

Save vectors of indices for transformation between x and v

Save the data file as an h5 file to be loaded in `run_AndAcc*.py`

Listing 2: Example make data file from NEMO-MEDUSA.

4.4 Timestepper

Typically very few edits are necessary in `timestepperfunc_*.py` other than to update function names, as read/write functions from `*_andacc_utils.py` are used within and named corresponding to the model being used. There are small differences in the format of `timestepperfunc_*.py` for ocean and land models arising from the need to run many instances of `andacc` simultaneously for land model spin up. If applying to a new model it will be best to start with the `timestepperfunc_*.py` function that is included from the most similar model we have applied `andacc` to. Below is an example `timestepperfunc_*.py` from NEMO-MEDUSA, annotated to include explanations. The user should adjust as needed for their ESM of choice.

```

1 from andacc import load, save, DotDict
2 import numpy as np
3 import os
4 from nemo_andacc_utils import NEMOIO
5
6 def timestepperfunc_nemo(x, y, fetchOutput, iter_, data, jobId, doSubmit):
7
8     NIO = NEMOIO()
9
10    gy=None
11
12    calcNorms = ("calcNorms" in data and data.calcNorms)
13
14    if x is not None:
15        iniFile="trini_{:04d}".format(jobId)
16        endFile="trend_{:04d}".format(jobId)
17
18    if (fetchOutput===-1) or (fetchOutput==0):
19        if "preprocess_cmd" in data:
20            if isinstance(data.preprocess_cmd, str):
21                os.system(data.preprocess_cmd)
22            elif callable(data.preprocess_cmd):
23                data.preprocess_cmd(jobId)
24            else:
25
26                raise Exception("ERROR: data.preprocess_cmd is neither callable nor
                a string!")
27
28    if x is not None:
29        NIO.writexy2NEMORestart(x, y, data, data.restartFileStart, isGlobal=
        data.isGlobal, writeTRB=data.writeTRB)
30
31    # we save this to compute norms and convergence later
32    if calcNorms:
33        if fetchOutput==0:
34            save({"v": v}, iniFile)
35        else:
36            v = NIO.v.copy()
37

```

Instantiate the utility class

The user can decide to calculate residual norms for individual tracers, set in `run_AndAcc*.py`

Optional pre-processing, set in `run_AndAcc*.py`

Here we write the AA iterate to the ESM restart file

Save the data to calculate norms if desired

```

38     if doSubmit:
39         print("Running model ...")
40         if isinstance(data.run_model_cmd, str):
41             os.system(data.run_model_cmd)
42         elif callable(data.run_model_cmd):
43             data.run_model_cmd(jobId)
44         else:
45             raise Exception("ERROR: data.run_model_cmd is neither callable nor a
46                 string!")
47
48         if "postprocess_cmd" in data:
49             if isinstance(data.postprocess_cmd, str):
50                 os.system(data.postprocess_cmd)
51             elif callable(data.postprocess_cmd):
52                 data.postprocess_cmd(jobId)
53             else:
54                 raise Exception("ERROR: data.postprocess_cmd is neither callable
55                     nor a string!")
56
57     if (fetchOutput==1) or (fetchOutput==0):
58         print("Finished running model")
59
60     # read gv from restart
61     gx, gy, gv=NIO.readFromNEMORestart2xy(data, data.restartFileEnd, isGlobal=
62         data.isGlobal)
63
64     # calculate norms
65     vnorms = np.linalg.norm(gv - v, axis=0)
66
67     with np.printoptions(suppress=False):
68         print(vnorms)
69
70     else:
71         vnorms = None
72
73     externalConvergence = DotDict()
74     if "externalConvergence" in data:
75         externalConvergence = data.externalConvergence(iter_, tmparr)
76         if not isinstance(externalConvergence, dict):
77             raise Exception(f"ERROR: function {data.externalConvergence} must
78                 return a dictionary!")
79
80     else:
81         return None
82
83     return gx, gy, vnorms, externalConvergence

```

Run the ESM using command set in `run_AndAcc*.py`

Optional post-processing, set in `run_AndAcc*.py`

Read model output to AA form, i.e. `g(x)`

Optional: run the external convergence check function set in `run_AndAcc*.py`

Return values to `andacc.py`, `gx = g(x)`

Listing 3: Example `timestepperfunc_*.py` from NEMO-MEDUSA.

4.5 Main Driver

This section is split for land and ocean models. The main `andacc` algorithm remains the same, but structure is different to account for running one global ocean simulation vs many independent soil columns. As mentioned in Section 1.2.4 for ocean models one instance of `andacc` is run, whereas for land models one instance of `andacc` is run for each soil column.

4.5.1 Ocean Models

The general structure of the main driver should require very little adjustment for ocean models. The workflow is fairly straightforward, and a user can follow the example drivers

that are included with the code. The primary edits necessary when applying to a new ocean model are to update file and function names, update the checkpointing function to ensure the correct information is read and saved as desired, update the external convergence check to ensure that the correct diagnostics are being checked, and update the `data.run_model_cmd` to correspond with the mpi call needed to run the model executable. Here we provide an annotated example of part of the `run_AndAcc*.py` driver for NEMO-MEDUSA.

```

1 #####
2 # BASIC SETTINGS #
3 #####
4 restartFileStart = "restart_trc.nc"
5 restartFileEnd = "ORCA2_00005840_restart_trc.nc" } Set the model restart file names
6 isGlobal=True
7
8 if len(sys.argv)>1:
9     restartFileStart = sys.argv[1]
10    restartFileEnd = sys.argv[2]
11
12 if len(sys.argv)>3:
13    isGlobal = (sys.argv[3] != "0")
14
15 #####
16 # PARAMETER SETTINGS #
17 #####
18 Aparams = DotDict() ← Setting algorithm parameters, see Section 3.3
19 Aparams.mMax = 50
20 Aparams.itmax = 3000
21 Aparams.beta = 1.0
22 Aparams.restartAANormStagnation = 0
23 Aparams.restartAANormDiff = 0.05
24 Aparams.restartAASuccessiveIters = 3
25 Aparams.restartAAPeriodic = 0
26 Aparams.startTime = time()
27 Aparams.wallTime=0.4*60*60
28
29 histParams = DotDict() ← Setting history parameters, see Section 3.4
30 histParams.nhistfreq = 20
31 histParams.nhistmax = ceil(Aparams.itmax / histParams.nhistfreq) + 5
32
33 doSubmit=1 ← Ensures timestepper runs the model, see Line 38 in Listing 3
34
35 iJob=1 ← Define job id, used in file naming
36
37 data=load("data_for_nemo_medusa_with_sed") ← Load data file set with
38                                           make_data_for_*.py
39
40 data.restartFileStart=restartFileStart
41 data.restartFileEnd=restartFileEnd
42 data.isGlobal=isGlobal
43 data.writeTRB=False
44 data.run_model_cmd="mpiexec -n 144 -ppn 48 ./nemo > log"
45 data.preprocess_cmd="mv ORCA2_00005840_restart_trc.nc restart_trc.nc"
46 data.postprocess_cmd="sleep 20" ← Setting pre and post process commands, for NEMO-
47 NIO = NEMOIO() ← MEDUSA we move files so the model reads the
48                                           correct restart. Will be different for each model
49
50 # Read initial condition from file
51 x0,y0,v=NIO.readFromNEMORestart2xy(data,"InitialCondition_10y/
52 ORCA2_00005840_restart_trc.nc",isGlobal) ← Use utility function to read initial model state
53
54 # On first job submission need to copy initial condition
55 os.system("cp -p InitialCondition_10y/ORCA2_00005840_restart_trc.nc
56 ORCA2_00005840_restart_trc.nc")
57
58 #####
59 # READING RESTARTS #
60 #####
61 fn="aa_restart_{:04d}".format(iJob)

```

```

59 if os.path.isfile(fn + ".h5"): ← Read andacc restarts if available to continue a spin up
60     print("Reading restart file")
61     s=load(fn) ← Load state from restart file with utility function
62 else:
63     s = AndersonAccelerationObj({}) ← Otherwise instantiate andacc state s
64
65 #####
66     # FUNCTION DEFINITIONS #
67 #####
68 def checkpointingFunction(i,s): ← Defining the checkpointing function, see Section 3.4.1.
69     This will change for a new model
70 ### CHECKPOINTING FUNCTION DEFINED HERE ###
71
72     return None
73
74 histParams.checkpointingFunction=checkpointingFunction ← Now add to histParams
75
76 def externalConvergenceCheck(i,s): ← Defining the external convergence checking function, see Section 3.1.1.
77     This will change for a new model
78 ### EXTERNAL CONVERGENCE CHECK FUNCTION DEFINED HERE ###
79
80     return None
81
82 data.externalConvergenceCheck = externalConvergenceCheck ← Add to data
83 #####
84     # RUNNING AA #
85 #####
86 g = lambda x, y, fetchOutput, iter_: timestepperfunc_nemo(x, y, fetchOutput,
87     iter_, data, iJob, doSubmit) ← Define the fixed point function using timestepperfunc_*.py
88 ret = andacc(g, x0, s, AParams, histParams, doRestart, suff, y0)
89 Call andacc to run accelerated spin up. Returns when solution found or wall time limit reached
90 xsol, iter_, ysol, converged = ret
91
92 #####
93     # POST PROCESSING #
94 #####
95 if not (np.array_equal(xsol,np.array([]))):
96     print("Saving solution")
97     tmparr, v = NIO.xy2nemo(xsol, ysol, data)
98     to_save = {'x0':x0, 'y0':y0, 'xsol':xsol, 'iter_':iter_, 'ysol':ysol, 'arr':
99         tmparr, 'converged':converged}
100     fn="andacc_solution_{:04d}".format(iJob)
101     save(to_save,fn)
102
103 fn="aa_restart_{:04d}".format(iJob)
104 save(s,fn) ← Save s for andacc restarting

```

Listing 4: Example partial **run_AndAcc*.py** driver for NEMO-MEDUSA.

4.5.2 Land Models

Here we describe the implementation of ‘alternating’ or ‘multi-stage’ **andacc** which is used for land models. Application to a new land model could require extensive rewriting, even if the general structure and approach remains as described here. CLM and JULES have proven to be quite different models, at least from a user interaction standpoint, meaning that while the general approach to each is the same, the implementation is somewhat different. If a user is applying this method to a new land model it is suggested that they use the JULES driver as a jumping off point and adjust as necessary to work with the model at hand. For land models the main driver file **run_AndAcc*.py** follows a similar setup structure to the one given in Listing 4. The ‘Basic Settings’ section will still include model basics like file names and locations, so we skip that here. The ‘Parameter Settings’ section will now need additional **AParams** style dictionaries for each **andacc** stage. For CLM two stages are used,

one with acceleration on soil tracers and one that allows for a DI adjustment period of *all* tracers.

JULES uses three stages, first a short acceleration of the soil temperature tracer, followed by alternating periods of AA and DI adjustment. Listing 5 gives an annotated example driver from JULES. The key point to understand is the main while loop defined on lines 179-213. The loop runs over all active land points, with each instance of **andacc** being called but waiting on a single dummy function to run the underlying ESM. This way the separate instances of **andacc** are all using the same model run. With JULES, the land points are all allowed to progress through each ‘stage’ independently, so if one soil column converges in the soil temperature stage before reaching the maximum allowed iterations it will simply move on to the next stage while the other land points continue in the soil temperature stage. This allows for maximum efficiency and capitalizes on the independence of columns.

```

22 numLand=4 ← Here we use 4 land points, so 4 instances of andacc
23
24 numAvgWindow=10 ← This is for the slope averaging convergence check, see Section 3.1.1
25
26 numStages=3 ← Define the total number of stages, here one for only soil temp, one for AA and one
27               for a DI adjustment
28
29 itmax=[25,200,50] ← Defining max iteration count for each stage
30 minNumItersForConvergence=[0,0,0]
31
32 nOuter=[4 for _ in range(numLand)]
33
34 restartFileStart = "input_data/historical.dump.19010101.0.nc"
35 # Note: data.restartFileEnd below is set to restartFileStart but we still need
36         the end filename
37 restartFileEnd = "output_data/historical.dump.19020101.0.nc"
38
39 Aparams = [DotDict() for _ in range(numStages)]
40
41 istg=0
42 Aparams[istg].mMax = 15
43 Aparams[istg].itmax = itmax[istg]
44 Aparams[istg].beta = 1.0
45 Aparams[istg].atol = 5.e-3
46 Aparams[istg].restartAANormStagnation = 0
47 Aparams[istg].restartAANormDiff = 0.05
48 Aparams[istg].restartAASuccessiveIters = 3
49 Aparams[istg].restartAAPeriodic = 0
50 Aparams[istg].startTime = time()
51 # Aparams[istg].wallTime = 11.5*60*60
52
53 istg=1
54 Aparams[istg].mMax = 15
55 Aparams[istg].itmax = itmax[istg]
56 Aparams[istg].beta = 1.0
57 # Aparams[istg].atol = 1.e-5
58 Aparams[istg].restartAANormStagnation = 0
59 Aparams[istg].restartAANormDiff = 0.05
60 Aparams[istg].restartAASuccessiveIters = 3
61 Aparams[istg].restartAAPeriodic = 0
62 Aparams[istg].startTime = time()
63 # Aparams[istg].wallTime = 11.5*60*60
64
65 istg=2
66 Aparams[istg].mMax = 0
67 Aparams[istg].itmax = itmax[istg]
68 Aparams[istg].beta = 1.0
69 Aparams[istg].restartAANormStagnation = 0
70 Aparams[istg].restartAANormDiff = 0.05
71 Aparams[istg].restartAASuccessiveIters = 3
72 Aparams[istg].restartAAPeriodic = 0
73 Aparams[istg].startTime = time()

```

} Assign parameters for each stage

```

72 # Aparams[istg].wallTime = 11.5*60*60
73
74 icStart=50
75 if icStart==0:
76     fn0="InitialCondition/historical.dump.19010101.0.nc"
77 # This is ugly; we initialize the counter to -1 the first time as it is
78 # incremented at the top
79 # of the checkpointing function so that the first file written has an index of
80 # 0
81 # iCount may be overwritten below for restarts
82 iCount=[-1 for _ in range(numLand)]
83 else:
84     fn0="DI1/history_for_restart_{:06d}.nc".format(icStart)
85 # iCount may be overwritten below for restarts
86 iCount=[icStart for _ in range(numLand)]
87
88 os.system(f"cp -p {fn0} {restartFileStart}")
89
90 ds=nc.Dataset(restartFileStart)
91 longitude=ds["longitude"][:].data[:]
92 latitude=ds["latitude"][:].data[:]
93 ds.close()
94
95 if os.path.isfile("restart_info.h5"):
96     print("Reading restart info file")
97     restart=load("restart_info.h5")
98     iCount=restart.iCount
99
100 dataStage=[] for _ in range(numStages)]
101
102 dataStage[0]=load("data_for_jules_only_soil_temp")
103 dataStage[1]=load("data_for_jules_only_n_inorg_ns_cs")
104 dataStage[2]=load("data_for_jules_all")
105
106 dataAll=dataStage[2]
107
108 # vscaleFac=np.ones(dataTempHum.numTracers)
109 # vscaleFac[dataTempHum.trNames.index("t_soil")]=100.0
110 # vscaleFac[dataTempHum.trNames.index("tsoil_deep")]=100.0
111 # dataTempHum.XToVScaleFac=np.diag(vscaleFac)
112 # dataTempHum.vToXScaleFac=np.diag(1./vscaleFac)
113
114 data=[] for _ in range(numStages)]
115 for istg in range(numStages):
116     data[istg]=[copy.deepcopy(dataStage[istg]) for _ in range(numLand)]
117     for il in range(numLand):
118         data[istg][il].iLand=il
119         data[istg][il].restartFileStart=restartFileStart
120         data[istg][il].restartFileEnd=restartFileEnd
121         data[istg][il].calcNorms=True
122         if il==0:
123             data[istg][il].run_model_cmd="mpirun -np 4 ./jules_double_all.exe &&
124                 log"
125
126 csavg=[] for _ in range(numLand)]
127
128 # Read initial condition from file
129 tmparr=[] for _ in range(numLand)]
130 x0=[] for _ in range(numLand)]
131 y0=[] for _ in range(numLand)]
132 v0=[] for _ in range(numLand)]
133 for il in range(numLand):
134     tmparr[il]=readFromJULESRestart(data[0][il].trNames, data[0][il].trDims,
135         data[0][il].iLand, restartFileStart)
136     x0[il],y0[il],v0[il]=jules2xy(tmparr[il],data[0][il])
137
138 def checkpointingFunction(i,s,il,istg):

```

Load data for each stage

```

135 ### DEFINE CHECKPOINTING FUNCTION ###
136     return None
137
138 def externalConvergenceCheck(i, arr, il, istg):
139 ### DEFINE EXTERNAL CONVERGENCE FUNCTION ###
140     return externalConvergence
141
142 g=[[[] for _ in range(numStages)] ← Need to define fixed point function g for each instance of
143 for istg in range(numStages):
144     g[istg]=[[] for _ in range(numLand)]
145     for il in range(numLand):
146         g[istg][il] = lambda x, y, fetchOutput, iter_: timestepperfunc_jules(x, y,
147                                     fetchOutput, iter_, data[istg][il], il, 0)
148 histParams=[[[] for _ in range(numStages)] ← Same for histParams
149 for istg in range(numStages):
150     histParams[istg]=[DotDict() for _ in range(numLand)]
151     for il in range(numLand):
152         histParams[istg][il].nhistfreq = -1
153         histParams[istg][il].checkpointingFunction=lambda i, s:
154             checkpointingFunction(i, s, il, istg)
155     if istg in (1,2):
156         for il in range(numLand):
157             data[istg][il].externalConvergence=lambda i, arr:
158                 externalConvergenceCheck(i, arr, il, istg)
159
160 # Filter out points without vegetation
161 iFrac=dataAll.trNames.index("frac")
162 Ifrac=np.ones((numLand))
163 for il in range(numLand):
164     frac=readFromJULESRestart([dataAll.trNames[iFrac]], [dataAll.trDims[iFrac]],
165                               il, restartFileStart)
166     if np.isclose(np.sum(frac[0][-4:]), 1.0):
167         Ifrac[il]=0
168
169 includeLandList=list(np.flatnonzero(Ifrac))
170 numIncludeLand=len(includeLandList)
171 excludeLandList=list(np.flatnonzero(Ifrac==0))
172 numExcludeLand=len(excludeLandList)
173
174 print(f"Excluding these land points because of frac condition: {
175       excludeLandList}")
176
177 iStage=[0 for _ in range(numLand)]
178 iOuter=[0 for _ in range(numLand)]
179
180 finishedJobs=np.zeros(numLand) ← Use this to keep track of which points have finished running
181 finishedJobs.flat[excludeLandList]=1
182 aa = [AndersonAccelerationObj({}) for _ in range(numLand)]
183 while np.any(finishedJobs==0): ← Main while loop, run until all points have finished
184     for il in includeLandList: ← Loop over the active land points
185         istg=iStage[il] ← Will run andacc using parameters for stage that the ilth land point is on
186         if not finishedJobs[il]:
187             suff="_{:02d}_{:06d}_{:04d}.h5".format(istg, iOuter[il], il)
188             print(f"Land point={il}: {iOuter[il]} {istg}")
189             xsol, iter_, ysol, converged = andacc(g[istg][il], x0[il], aa[il],
190                                                 AAparams[istg], histParams[istg][il], 1, suff, y0[i
191             l])
192             if not np.array_equal(xsol, np.array([])):
193                 # Insert final iterate into (start) restart file
194                 tmparr[il], v=xy2jules(aa[il].x, aa[il].y, data[istg][il])
195                 writeToJULESRestart(data[istg][il].trNames, data[istg][il].trDims,
196                                     tmparr[il], data[istg][il].iLand, data[istg][il].
197                 restartFileStart)
198                 print(f"Land point {il} finished stage {istg} at outer {iOuter[il]}")
199                 iStage[il]=iStage[il]+1 ← If stage returns solution move on to next stage
200                 if iStage[il]==numStages:

```

```

195         iOuter[il]=iOuter[il]+1
196         if iOuter[il]==nOuter[il]:
197             finishedJobs[il]=1
198             print(f"Land point {il} finished outer {iOuter[il]}")
199         else:
200             iStage[il]=0
201         if not finishedJobs[il]:
202             istg=iStage[il]
203 #         Then pull out variables for next stage from same (start) restart
204         file.
205         tmparr[il]=readFromJULESRestart(data[istg][il].trNames, data[istg][
206             il].trDims, data[istg][il].iLand, data[istg][il
207             ].restartFileStart)
208         x0[il],y0[il],v0[il]=jules2xy(tmparr[il],data[istg][il])
209         aa[il]=AndersonAccelerationObj({})
210 #     check again
211     if np.any(finishedJobs==0):
212         os.system(f"rm -f {restartFileEnd}")
213         gfunc = lambda x, y, fetchOutput: timestepperfunc_jules(x,y,fetchOutput,0,
214             data[0][0],None,1) ← Define dummy function to run the ESM, all points will read result
215         gfunc(None,None,0) ← This actually runs the ESM

```

Listing 5: Example partial `run_AndAcc*.py` driver for JULES.

4.6 Submission Script

A spin up is run by submitting an HPC submission script to the batch queuing system. The submission script is very simple, typically it will just require loading the necessary modules from the user's HPC, and then calling `python run_AndAcc.py >> log_aa`. During runtime `andacc.py` and `run_AndAcc*.py` will output various diagnostics or updates with print statements, so piping the output into a log is helpful for monitoring progress or debugging if errors occur. Listing 6 gives an example submission script for running AA for CLM on Derecho.

```

1  #!/bin/bash
2  #PBS -N RUN_NAME
3  #PBS -A PROJECT_CODE
4  #PBS -l walltime=12:00:00
5  #PBS -q main           Request the resources needed to run the underlying model
6  #PBS -j oe
7  #PBS -l select=1:ncpus=125:mpiprocs=125:ompthreads=1:mem=230GB
8
9
10 export TMPDIR=$SCRATCH/temp
11 mkdir -p $TMPDIR
12
13 set -e
14
15 module --force purge
16 module load ncarenv
17 module load conda
18 conda activate npl-2023a
19 module load gcc/12.2.0
20 module load cray-mpich
21 module load ncarcompilers
22 module load hdf5-mpi
23 module load netcdf-mpi
24
25
26 export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=$LD_LIBRARY_PATH:$NCAR_LDFLAGS_HDF5:
27     $NCAR_LDFLAGS_NETCDF
28 python -u run_AndAcc_for_CLM.py >> log_aa ← Call the driver script run_AndAcc*.py

```

and send the output to a log file

Listing 6: Example submission script for `andacc` for CLM.

4.7 Algorithm Tuning

Algorithm performance can be extremely sensitive to a myriad of tuning parameters. It has been found that there are commonalities across ESMs modeling the same underlying system. For example, for both CLM and JULES it has been found that alternating periods of accelerated spin up on *only* soil BGC tracers, followed by a DI adjustment period where all tracers are allowed to evolve leads to the best performance. The purpose of this section is to give explanations of the meaning of various tune-able parameters, and provide and comments on past experience with them.

4.7.1 Memory

The primary place to start for tuning is with the Anderson memory parameter `mMax`. As indicated in Section 1.1 this controls the number of previous iterates that are used in the linear combination to form the next iterate. In testing ocean models have tended to be relatively robust to choice of memory parameter, with $m = 50$ offering a good balance of performance without excessive CPU memory needs. For higher resolution setups this will likely need to be reduced to $m = 25 - 30$ in order to ensure the job does not run out of CPU memory. In parameter optimization testing for ocean models they have always preferred the maximum allowed memory, while for land models $m = 15$ has offered the best performance on both CLM and JULES. We do not currently have a good explanation as to why ocean models prefer to have more memory than land models, but it is worth noting that in the Anderson literature it is rare to see a memory parameter over $m = 10$, so the ocean models are the outlier.

4.7.2 Damping

Again we recall from Section 1.1 that β represents the damping parameter. It is helpful to think of β as a control on the step size. In mathematical terms the algorithm is calculating a direction in which it thinks best to move. With $\beta = 1$, the ‘full’ Anderson step is taken, but a shorter step in the same direction can be taken with $\beta < 1$. In `andacc` this is set with `beta` in the `AAparams` structure at the top of `run_AndAcc*.py`. Included in `andacc` is the possibility to assign a function to `beta` if the user wishes to apply adaptive damping. It is suggested to begin with no damping, i.e. `beta=1`, and we have typically not found a benefit from applying damping on ocean or land model spin up.

4.7.3 Tracer Scaling

As mentioned in Section 1.3.5 it is possible to add scalings to tracer values to up or down-weight the importance of certain tracers, or to normalize the order of magnitude of tracer values that are combined into one column vector. Mathematical intuition would suggest that ensuring all tracers are scaled to $\mathcal{O}(1)$ would yield the best performance, but experiments doing just that have not led to the best performance. In fact, after applying the hyperparameter autotuner GPTune [7, 6, 3] to tune tracer scaling for NEMO-MEDUSA it was found that scaling up the importance of oxygen and down the importance of iron, despite iron begin $\mathcal{O}(1e-3)$ and oxygen $\mathcal{O}(1e2)$, gave the best performance. Given the complexity of approaching this scaling problem it is suggested to begin without any scaling, and later use an autotuning method to find ideal scalings.

Remark 3 While performance on NEMO-MEDUSA with ideal scalings was improved, it was not significant over an unscaled approach, and a user is suggested to begin with an unscaled version.

4.7.4 Alternating or Multi-Stage `andacc`

We use ‘alternating’ or ‘multi-stage’ `andacc` to describe the procedure that is used in accelerating CLM and JULES. In this setup portions of acceleration are alternated with portions of DI adjustment. The idea behind this is to accelerate a select group of tracers into a pseudo-equilibrium, then allow those to interact with the remaining tracers that evolve more quickly. In practice for CLM the slow evolving soil column tracers are accelerated with all other tracers held fixed, then acceleration is turned off and the entire model evolves together briefly. A similar approach is used for JULES.

This approach has not been tested on ocean models, as it does add complexity and performance was already good with a standard approach that accelerates all tracers. With the added complexity comes added tuning opportunity, as the user must set the number of iterations in each portion of the spin up. The duration spent in accelerated mode or DI mode that yields the best performance is vastly different between JULES and CLM. For JULES far longer periods of acceleration, $\mathcal{O}(100)$ years, and fewer total cycles yield good performance, whereas for CLM short 25 iteration bursts of acceleration followed by 10 year adjustment periods yield the best performance. It is suggested that the user begin with a standard `andacc` approach to begin, and then move to an alternating `andacc` approach if necessary.

4.7.5 Other Options

From experience running `andacc` on NEMO-MEDUSA it was found that there were occasional periods of acceleration plateauing. As a response the parameter `restartAAPeriodic` was set to flush memory history and restart every 150 iterations, which cured the plateauing issues. Thus far `andacc` flushing has not been necessary for land models, and performance without periodic memory flushing on MEDUSA is still satisfactory.

Finally, as indicated in Section 1.3.2, the user may include tracers that get accelerated passively, or simply copied over each iteration. This is accomplished with the ‘`y`’ vector, which may be set in `make_data_for_*.py`. In `run_AndAcc*.py` the user can also set `applyAAtoY` to true or false, depending on if they want the tracers in `y` to be accelerated or simply copied. As a reminder, when `y` tracers are accelerated the Anderson step direction is chosen *exclusively* based on the `x` tracer, so there is no guarantee that the direction chosen is beneficial for `y`. This feature hasn’t been shown to have significant benefit in testing thus far, so is generally unused, but could be a direction for users to research in the future.

4.7.6 GPTune

As mentioned in Section 4.7.3 we have applied the hyperparameter autotuner GPTune to find ideal tracer scalings, memory parameter, damping parameter, and periodic `andacc` memory flushing parameter for MITgcm-Bling and NEMO-MEDUSA. The parameters found by GPTune did offer the best performance, but did not lead to such significant gains over ‘default’ parameters that it is necessary to use. Readers are directed to [7, 6, 3] for more on GPTune.

4.8 Utility functions

Interaction with model restart files is done with the utility class defined in `*_andacc_utils.py`. This class contains functions for reading and writing to model restarts and for transition between different AA specific linear algebra structures. In general, when applying AA to a new model these functions must be rewritten to account for differences in restart file format. This class is used throughout the AA python files. Also included in the package are the `load` and `save` functions defined in `andacc.py` and described in Section 1.3.4.

Typically the only functions in `*_andacc_utils.py` that require much rewriting for a new model are the `writeToESMRestart` and `readFromESMRestart` functions. For user’s familiar

with their model’s restart file format this should be very easy to do. The rest of the functions in `*_andacc_utils.py` should remain nearly unchanged, although the user must ensure function names match.

5 Outputs and Post Processing

5.1 Outputs

In general **andacc** will write out restart files, checkpoint files, solution files, and text log files. A user may wish for additional files to be written out each step as is discussed in Section 3.4.1, but here we focus on the default categories.

5.1.1 Restart Files

Over the course of a spinup the ability to stop and restart is crucial to remain in compliance with HPC rules and wall time limits. When **andacc** reaches the user specified wall time limit it will write out a restart file for each instance of **andacc** that is run. E.g. an ocean model will write out a single restart file, where as a land model will write out one restart file for each point. The restart file contains the state of the algorithm `s`, and thus all of the information necessary to pick up where the algorithm left off and keep an entirely deterministic solution path. From a user’s point of view nothing is required, **andacc** automatically will save the restart files, and the user need only resubmit the HPC job runscrip to continue a spin up.

5.1.2 Checkpoint Files

andacc can optionally write out periodic checkpoint files. These files are essentially the same as restarts but with a coinciding model restart file as well, to ensure that a user can return to the exact same ESM state. These checkpoints are designed to ensure that progress is periodically saved in case of an unforeseen crash, e.g. HPC unscheduled downtime or an mpi error. These files can be quite large because model restarts are copied, so in a production run it is unlikely that checkpointing will happen often. However, checkpointing adds a layer of safety on long runs so the user need not restart entirely if something goes wrong. The user can see lines 21-30 in Listing 1 for an example.

5.1.3 Solution Files

The current spin up solution can be written out in the checkpointing function. In the example shown for NEMO-MEDUSA in Listing 1 the current solution is written out every 10 iterations (see lines 14-18) to save space, but a user may wish for the exact solution more or less often depending on their research goals. The spinup solution file typically contains the iteration count as well as the **andacc** vectors `x` and `y`, as well as any user specified additions.

5.1.4 Log Files

In addition to the files described above the output from the underlying ESM is sent to a text file called `log` and the output from **andacc** is sent to a text file called `log_aa`. On each iteration **andacc** will print out information on the residual, tracer norms if desired, ESM flux diagnostics (e.g. Listing 1 line 13), or more as customized by the user. The `log_aa` file is helpful for quickly assessing progress of the spin up, but it can become quite large and cumbersome for land models with thousands of instances of **andacc** running together. The user can customize print outputs in the `run_AndAcc*.py` script as they desire, but no modifications are required.

5.2 Post Processing

Included in the package are a few example post processing scripts to help with combining solution and diagnostic files written out each iteration into one larger file for ease of plotting and analysis. These scripts will need to be modified for the user's purpose but work as a good jumping off point.

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